

Effect of Low and High Temperature Regimes on the germination of Carrot seeds (*Daucus carota L.*) using Thermal-time model

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Abstract

The establishment of carrot crop is by direct seeding, poor seeds emergence may occur when seed sowing is done at extremely low or high temperatures. This study therefore, determined the effect of temperature regimes (high and low) in breaking dormancy and on germination rate of carrot seeds using thermal-time model. The seeds of carrot (*Daucus carota*) were purchased from market in Wudil, Kano state. Two temperature regimes treatment experiment were considered and categorized into two (A and B), seeds treated with hot water and other seeds treated with cold water respectively. The experiment was arranged as 2x4x3 factorial treatment structure in a completely randomized design (CRD). Ten seeds each from group A and B were treated at various temperatures of 47°C, 42°C, 37°C and 32°C and 17°C, 12°C, 7°C and 2°C respectively and each for the duration of 5, 10 and 15 seconds. Out of 221 total rate of germination recorded during the study, low temperature regime shows significant ($P < 0.05$) highest rate of germination at 17°C with 31.7% rate of germination (RG) as compared to the high temperature regime. The overall results showed that, the low temperature regime had a relative positive effect on the rate of germination of the seeds, most especially at 17°C which may be regarded as the overall optimum temperature for the seed germination. In conclusion, delayed seedling emergence are the major threats in the production of carrots in the Northern part of Nigeria, most especially Kano due to extreme low and high temperatures of the area.

Key words; carrot seed, cold water, germination, hot water, temperature regime, thermal-time

Email: chrissaliuodeje@gmail.com

Received: August 10, 2023

Revised: September 21, 2023

Accepted: September 26, 2023

About the Journal: SJANS is a multidisciplinary science journal and the official journal of the Faculty of Science, Nigeria Police Academy, Kano, Nigeria

1.0 Introduction

The establishment of Carrot crop is reported to be by direct seeding, and poor emergence and stands may occur when seed sowing is done during extremely low or high temperatures. Many publications relate the negative effects of high temperatures (35-40°C) on carrot stand establishment, because temperature plays a major role in determining the periodicity of seed germination and the distribution of species (Vieira *et al.*, 2005; Pereira *et al.*, 2007 and Nascimento *et al.*, 2008). In germination process the seeds role is that of a reproductive unit, its property of life that assures the survival of all plant species. Furthermore because of its role in stand establishment, seed germination remains a key to modern agriculture practice as a general rule (Finch-Savage, *et al.*, 2001 and Rajasekaran *et al.*, 2002). On the other hand, it is also believed that low temperatures associated with long days induce early bolting, but lack of adequate knowledge on the suitable temperature for the production of carrot by cultivators has greatly affected the primary production of the crop in Kano, Nigeria. The dry season is considered the most critical season in the northern part of Nigeria where there is no adequate rainfall for the growth of carrot

crops, which may result to lack of the product in the market, with a consequent rise in price. (Vieira *et al.*, 2005). With regards to the above mentioned problems, this study has therefore birthed the need to carry out the research on the effect of temperature regimes (high and low) using the thermal-time model in breaking seed dormancy and germination rate of carrot seed.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Description of the study area

This research study was conducted at Nigeria Police Academy (POLAC) in Wudil Local Government Area Kano State Nigeria, which is located in East Central area of Kano State, and in the central area of Kano Region between longitude 8° 45'E, as well as between latitude 11° 37'N and latitude 11° 56'N. Wudil is 35Km from Kano along Kano-Maiduguri road. The mean annual rainfall is about 884mm varying greatly from as low as 600mm in the north to 1200 mm in the Southern tips. On the average, the wettest month is August, which has the highest number of rainstorms and sediment generation while the mean annual temperature ranges from 26°C to 32°C, with the high diurnal temperature ranges of 13.1°C and

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

relative humidity of 17% - 90% (Kowal and Knabe, 1972; Olofin, 1987).

2.2 Procurement and viability test of the seeds

The processed and package seeds of carrot (*Daucus carota*) was purchased from an open market in Wudil, Kano state. It was authenticated by a Botanist in the Department of Biological Sciences, Nigeria Police Academy Wudil, Kano. The viability of the seeds was tested in accordance with the methods of Germ (1975) and Copeland (1976).

2.3 Experimental Design and procedure

The study consist of two temperature regimes treatment experiment (ie low and high) arranged as 2x4x3 factorial treatment structure in a completely randomized design(CRD).Each of the 12 experimental units were replicated twice given a total of 24 experimental units. The temperature regimes treatment factor was categorized into two (A and B), the seeds treated with hot water and the seeds treated with cold water respectively. Four (4) temperature regulated intervals factor for both Low and High temperature regimes and also three (3) regulated time (Duration) factor in seconds were used.

2.4 Experimentation

Ten seeds from group A were treated with hot water at various temperature intervals of 47°C, 42°C, 37°C and 32°C and each for the duration of 5,10 and 15seconds .The same number of seeds were also used for group B, and were treated with chilled (cold) water obtained from a refrigerator at the temperature intervals of 17 °C, 12°C ,7° C and 2°C for same duration in seconds .A folded wire gauze with a handle was used in removing the seeds from hot and cold waters in to separate containers with distilled water for 5 minutes, and thereafter spread on a white paper to be sun-dried for 4 hours before planting experiment. The seeds planting experiment were performed in 24 polythene pots packed with composited sandy-loam soil with an ambient temperature of 24°C.Ten (10) seeds per pot were planted at a depth of 1.5cm for all the replicates. The potted seeds and seedlings were lightly watered twice a day (morning and evening) to ensured adequate

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

water supply for germination. Seeds were considered to have germinated when the tips of the radical has grown free above the soil, and the% rate of germination(in term of number of leaves) for each plant category were also recorded and calculated at the interval of three days after germination .The number of leaves was calculated using the formula prescribed by Abubakar and Maimuna (2013)

$$NL = \frac{Tnl}{Tnsem}$$

Where: **NL** = Number of leaves

Tnl = Total number of leaves on a particular plant

Tnsem = Total number of seeds emerged.

2.5 Statistical analysis

The percentage rate of germination was determined by dividing the total number of seeds germinated (**N**) over the total number of seeds sown in the pot-polythene (**TNSS**), and multiplying the product by hundred (**100**). Data obtained during the study were subjected to Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and the mean values were compared using Ducan multiple range test described by Steel and Torrie (1980) using a Statistical Software package for Social sciences (SPSS) version 19.

Plate 1: Showing the Carrot seeds (*Daucus carota*)

Plate2: Showing the Carrot seedling emergence

3.1 The Result of the Temperature Regime on the Emergence of Carrot Seeds at Regulated Time(S)

The result of the temperature regimes on the emergence of carrot seed at regulated time in seconds is presented in Table1. Out of 82 total number of seed emergence, low temperature regime had significant ($p < 0.05$) highest percentage seed emergence (SDE) of 21.95% at the temperature of 17°C and lowest percentage seed emergence (SDE) of 8.54% recorded at 2°C. Meanwhile, high temperature regime also had a significant ($P < 0.05$) highest percentage (SDE) of 12.20% at 32°C and the lowest percentage (SDE) of 7.32% recorded at 42°C and 47°C. The overall result showed that, most seeds emergences are recorded at the regulated time of 5 and 10 seconds.

3.0 Results and Discussion

Table1: Effect of temperature regimes on the emergence of Carrot seeds at regulated times

Temperature Regime (°C)	Seed Emergence at Regulated Time(s)			Freq.	Total	% SDE	MSTD
	[5]	[10]	[15]				
Low:	2	6	1	0	7	8.54	2.33±.38 ^c
	7	5	8	0	13	15.85	4.33±.51 ^b
	12	6	4	4	14	17.07	4.67±.86 ^b
	17	5	6	7	18	21.95	6.00±.83 ^a
High:	32	5	4	1	10	12.20	3.33±.70 ^{bc}
	37	5	3	0	08	9.75	2.67±.52 ^c
	42	3	2	1	06	7.32	2.00±.82 ^d
	47	2	2	2	06	7.32	2.00±.89 ^d
Total		37	30	15	82		

Note: All values with same letter superscript are not significantly different at $p < 0.05$

% SDE = Percentage seed emergence = Number of individual seed emergence per pot / Total seeds emergence x 100
MSTD = Mean value standard deviation in triplicate

3.2 Measuring the rate of germination of carrot seeds in 3 days interval of observation

The rate of germination of carrot seeds in 3 days interval of observation was measured and recorded in Table 2. A total of 221 rate of germination was observed and recorded during the study. The low temperature regime shows significant ($P < 0.05$) highest rate of germination

at 17°C having a total number of 70 leaves with 31.7% rate of germination (RG), while significant lowest rate of germination was observed and recorded at 2°C showing a total of 27 leaves with 12.3% RG. Moreover, the result for high temperature regime also reveals significant ($p < 0.05$) highest rate of germination at 32°C having the total of 24 leaves with 10.9% RG,

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

meanwhile, the lowest RG was observed and recorded at 42 and 47°C, giving the total of 12 leaves with 5.4 % RG each. The overall results for the effect of both low and high temperature regimes showed clearly that, the low temperature regime had a relative positive effect on the rate of germination of the seeds, most especially at 17°C which may be regarded as the overall optimum temperature for the seed germination.

Table 2: Measurement of the Rate of Germination of Carrot Seeds after Three Days Interval of Observation

Temperature Regime (°c)	RG at days Interval			Total, N	% Mean	RG	STD
	D3	D6	D9				
LOW:	2	14	4	9	27	12.22	9.00±.92 ^{bc}
	7	8	18	4	30	13.58	10.00±.63 ^b
	12	14	8	8	30	13.58	10.00±.85 ^b
	17	10	22	38	70	31.67	23.33±.73 ^a
HIGH	32	10	8	6	24	10.86	8.00±.82 ^c
	37	8	4	4	16	7.24	5.00±.86 ^d
	42	6	4	2	12	5.43	4.00±.78 ^{de}
	47	4	4	4	12	5.43	4.00±.85 ^{de}
TOTAL		74	72	75	221(TNSS)		

Note: Mean – value with same letter superscript are not significantly different. D3; D6; D9 = Day 3, 6, and 9 respectively.

%RG (%Rate of germination in terms of number of leaves) = total number of seeds germinated (N) over the total number of seeds sown in the pot-polythene (TNSS), and multiplying the product by hundred (100).

3.3 Determination of thermal-time model for low and high temperature regimes for germination of seeds at sub and supra optimal temperatures

The result for determination of thermal-time model for low and high temperature regimes for germination at sub and supra optimal temperatures reveals some of the measurement parameters during the study as presented in Table 3. For low temperature regime, the sub optimal temperature (**To₁**) was at 17°C, which was the temperature where germination most occurred, the base temperature (**Tb**) at 2°C was the critical or lowest temperature at which germination occurred. The time required for the germination fraction (**g**) of the population to

germinate, was 5 seconds and **Tt** (**g₁**) was the thermal – time in degree – days (°Cd) was determined as 110 (°Cd) with the % **SDE** of 22.2%. Meanwhile, the result for high temperature regime, recorded the supra optimal temperature (**To₂**) at 32°C, which was also observed to be the temperature where most germination rate occurred, the maximum temperature (**Tc**) at which seeds germination occurred was recorded at 47°C. And the thermal – time determined was 115 (°Cd) with the % **SDE** of 12.2%. Although, the actual temperature (**T**) for both temperature regimes was 24°C and also the germination rate for a given fraction (**tg**) for both temperature regimes was 0.2.

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

Table 3: Determination of Thermal – time Model for Low and High Temperature regimes for Germination of seeds at Sub – and Supra optimal Temperature.

Temperature Regime (°C)	Measurement Parameters							
	T(°Cd)	Tc	Tb(°C)	To(°C)	tg	G.R(g)	Tt(°Cd)	%SDE
LOW:	24	-	2	17	5	0.2	110	22.0
HIGH:	24	47	-	32	5	0.2	115	12.2

T = Actual temperature at which the seeds can germinate. To = Optimum Temperature (Sub & Supra).

Tc = Max or ceiling temperature which is the highest temperature at which seeds can germinate.

Tb = Lowest temperature at which germination occur. SDE = Seed Emergence Rate.

tg = Time required for the germinating fraction (g) of the population to germinate.

G.R = Germination Rate. Tt (g₂) = Thermal – time in degree – days at high temperature regime.

Tt (g₁) = Thermal – time in degree – days at low temperature regime.

3.4 Discussion

Temperature regimes have significant effect on the overall rate of germination of carrot seeds (*Daucus carota*) most especially at low temperature regime of 17°C at a regulated time interval of 5 seconds. Germination rate (GR) was invariably observed to be low at low temperatures, but gradually increases as temperature also rises to optimum temperature range (17 to 32°C) which was the sub and supra temperature respectively. This finding is in agreement with other related works reported on carrot seed germination, and this further explain that, the relatives low %GR recorded during this study at low temperatures may possibly be as the result of limited water flow, reduction in the rate of thermo chemical reaction in the seeds and change in the configuration of water molecules. These might have then resulted to reduced availability of water, causing delaying in seed inhibition, reducing the synthesis of cell wall loosening factors, and affecting turgor potential during radicle emergency phase of seed germination (Bradford, 2002). The critical temperature (Tb) recorded at 2°C, was the lowest temperature at which carrot seeds germination occurred during the study. This finding is in deviant with the one reported by Rajasekaran *et al.*, (2002), hence the sporadic emergence of the potted- grown carrot seedlings, which may be due to low temperature of the soil during seed sowing. Vereira *et al.*, (2005), Briscoe, *et al.*, (2006) and Pereira, (2007), in their related publications reported the negative effect of extreme low temperature on carrot seed establishment. However, high temperature above 40°C may also delay or even inhibit carrot seed germination and thereby reducing the chances of uniformity and total stand establishment of the carrot, (Nascimento and Pereira, (2007). This

also implies that, in tropical areas such as Kano in Nigeria where carrot production is mostly high may face the problem of being vulnerable to lost in yield due to thermo stress (High temperature) during stand establishment as similarly reported by Vereira *et al.*, (2005).

Conclusion

In conclusion, Sporadic and delayed seedling emergence are reported to be as major threats in the production of carrots in the Northern part of Nigeria, most especially Kano dues to extreme low and high temperature regimes of the areas resulting in a reduced crop stand establishment, directly lowering the root yield and quality of the commercial carrot cultivars, Among the factors that control seed germination, temperature is the most important factor that regulates the timing of seed germination. And as observed during this study, GR was invariably observed to be low at low temperatures, but gradually increases as temperature also rises to optimum temperature range (17 to 32°C) which was the sub and supra temperature respectively

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